

New records of Crambidae (Insecta, Lepidoptera) from Omsk Region

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Abstract

Four species of Crambidae are reported from the territory of Omsk Region of Russia. *Titanio ledereri* (Staudinger, 1870) is new to Asian part of Russia, *Loxostege peltalis* (Eversmann, 1842), *Catoptria verellus* (Zincken, 1817) and *Ostrinia peregrinalis* (Eversmann, 1852) are new to West Siberia.

Keywords

Lepidoptera, Crambidae, West Siberia, Omsk Region, fauna, new records

Introduction

The local fauna of Crambidae of Omsk Region includes 90 species (Knyazev et al. 2014, 2016, 2017, 2019; Knyazev and Ponomaryov 2019). In the collecting season 2021 we collect four species which were not presented on the territory of Omsk Region earlier. Three of them are new to the territory of West Siberia and one – new to the Asian Part of Russia. These materials became the basis of this article.

Materials and methods

All material processed within the framework of this article was collected on the territory of the Omsk region in 2021 by authors using the standard method by butterfly net and by using mercury lamps 250W. The identification of the material was carried out using modern keys and taxonomic revisions. All specimens were deposited in collections of Svyatoslav Knyazev (SKO, Omsk, Russia) and Konstantin Ponomaryov (KPO, Omsk, Russia).

Results

Catoptria verellus (Zincken, 1817)

(Fig. 1–1)

Material examined. 4♂, Muromtsevsky district, Petropavlovka vill. vic., 56°24'1.13"N, 75°16'6.85"E, at light, 10-11.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKO).

Remark. First record of the species in West Siberia. Forest species, locally distributed in Europe, Asia Minor, European Part of Russia, South Ural, Russian Far East – Amur region, South of Khabarovsk Territory, Primorye, Sakhalin (Slamka 2008; Sinev 2019). In the Omsk Region specimens were collected in mixed forest (*Betula pendula*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Populus tremula*, *Sorbus aucuparia*) at night time by a mercury lamp.

Titanio ledereri (Staudinger, 1870)

(Fig. 1–2)

Material examined. 1♂, Cherlacksy district, Solyanoye vill. vic., 54°21'4.40"N, 74°38'2.06"E, in the grass, 11.VII.2021, K.B. Ponomarev (KPO).

Remark. First record of the species in the Asian Part of Russia and the second find in Russia. Rare and local species which is known by old materials from Europe (Hungary, Italy, Romania, Turkey), Ukraine (Yepishin et al. 2020), and from Ulyanovsk Region in Russia only (Zolotuhin 2005; Slamka 2006; Sinev 2019). The specimen from Omsk Region was collected in the south of the forest-steppe zone in a daytime by a butterfly net mowing on the grass.

Loxostege peltalis (Eversmann, 1842)

(Fig. 1–3)

Material examined. 1♂, Russko-Polyansky district, 8 km SW of Khlebodarovka vill., river Tleusai, 53°42'7.53"N, 73°25'11.71"E, at light, 12.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev (SKO).

Remark. First record of the species in the Asian Part of Russia. Rare and local steppe species, distributed in Volga Region and South Ural in Russia (Sinev 2019), also known from Turkey and Kirghizia (Slamka 2013). The specimen from Omsk Region was collected in the steppe zone at night time by mercury lamp in May.

Figure 1. **1** – *Catoptria verellus*, Petropavlovka, 10-11.VII.2021 (SKO); **2** – *Titanio ledereri*, Solyanoye, 11.VII.2021 (KPO); **3** – *Loxostege peltalis*, Khlebodarovka, 12.V.2021 (SKO); **4** – *Ostrinia peregrinalis*, Karbyza, 22.V.2021 (SKO).

****Ostrinia peregrinalis* (Eversmann, 1852)**

(Fig. 1-4)

Material examined. 1♂, Muromtsevsky district, 7 km NNW of Karbyza vill., 56°39'14.26"N, 75°52'16.98"E, 22.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina (SKO).

Remark. First record of the species in West Siberia. Local and rare species in Europe where it is known in Estonia (Slamka 2013). In Russia, it is distributed in the Urals, Krasnoyarsk territory, Baikal region, South Yakutia, Kamchatka, Amur, South of Khabarovsk Territory, Primorye. The specimen from Omsk Region was collected in the forest zone in the daytime on the grass.

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